

BUILDING SHARED KNOWLEDGE: LEARNING ABOUT LANGUAGE THROUGH DETAILED READING

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Abstract: *Collaboration, integration of content and language are the main bases of learning foreign language through detailed reading moreover skills of learning language is considered a vulnerable process demanding to fulfill a number of processes likewise detailed reading which consists of following inner structures presenting, enacting relationships and constructing a cohesive messages.*

Key words: *detailed reading, cohesive reading, constituents, enactive relationships, deconstruction*

This phase includes a strategy entitled Detailed Reading (de Oliveira et al., 2015). This strategy is often part of the Deconstruction phase of the TLC. However, we believe that detailed reading should occur as students are building shared knowledge about the content to be explored so we have included this as part of building shared knowledge. Teachers select a short excerpt or short text to explore with students that includes content that is important for students to learn, addressing state content standards. Students and teacher explore how the text is written and how it accomplishes its goals through its language choices. *Detailed Reading* focuses on classroom interactions with students, conducting read-alouds, identifying language features, focusing on grammatical expressions, target vocabulary, and main ideas. They focus on three areas of meaning: *presenting content, enacting relationships, and constructing a cohesive message* and teacher and students explore the text as it is written, without any simplification (de Oliveira & Schleppegrell, 2015). Table 1 presents these three areas of meaning, questions to guide language discussion, and the focus of language related to each area of meaning, described in more detail next.

Table 1

Detailed Reading: Areas of Meaning, Questions, and Focus of Analysis

Area of Meaning	Question to Guide Language Discussion	Focus of Language
Presenting content	What is happening? Who are the people or things involved? What are the circumstances surrounding events?	Sentence Constituents: Participants, processes, circumstances
Enacting relationships	What are the roles and relationships taken up by participants?	Mood choices: Declarative Interrogative Imperative Modality
Constructing a cohesive message	How is the text organized? How is the language used?	Theme/New Cohesion

Note. Table is based on de Oliveira and Schleppegrell's (2015) previous work.

Presenting content explores the Participants (typically expressed through nouns) engaged in some kinds of Processes (typically expressed through verbs) under certain Circumstances (typically expressed through prepositional and adverbial phrases; Eggins, 2004; Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). Participants are the entities involved in the process, typically realized in noun groups (e.g., *the magnet, many metal objects, a scientific phenomenon*), and these participants take on different semantic roles in different process types. There are four major process types, expressed through verbs: **doing verbs** that represent actions such as *participate* and *run*; **relating verbs** that show relationships between ideas such as *is* and *has*; **thinking verbs** that represent thought such as *think, know, consider*; **feeling verbs** that represent feelings such as *admire, love, like*; and **saying verbs** that indicate what someone or something has said such as *say, tell, ask*. Processes also take place around circumstances (of time, space, conditions, purpose etc.), typically realized in adverbs (e.g., *finally, separately*) or prepositional phrases (e.g., *around the corner, with a fork*). Teacher and students explore participants, processes, and circumstances in clauses to reveal how content is presented.

Enacting relationships explores mood and modality. We can look at the presence or absence of the subject and finite elements of the clauses and in what order they occur with respect to one another (Halliday &

Matthiessen, 2014). These are important because they realize the grammatical choice of the *mood* of a clause: either declarative, interrogative, or imperative. The mood system allows us to make statements (typically expressed in declarative mood), ask questions (typically expressed in interrogative mood), and declare commands (typically expressed in imperative mood). Another aspect is *modality*, an area which concerns the different ways in which someone expresses evaluation, attitudes, and judgments of various kinds. Modality allows us to express possibility, certainty, normality, usuality, necessity, and obligation. This includes modal verbs (e.g., *should, might, could*), modal adjectives (e.g., *frequent, usual*), modal adverbs (e.g., *probably, certainly, typically*), and modal nouns (e.g., *condition, necessity*). Evaluative vocabulary enables the construction of stance and judgment. Mood, modality, and evaluative vocabulary express meanings that enact a relationship between reader and listener and writer and speaker.

Constructing a cohesive message explores Given/New patterns. Given is the first experiential element of the clause and the New encompasses the remaining bit of the clause (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). Additionally, it is useful to track the given patterns (also called thematic development) through texts which, in part, helps organize the overall text as it moves from stage to stage and within the stage. Another important area of to explore is cohesion, the way a text hangs together with the support of cohesive devices such as pronouns (e.g., they, that, her), synonyms and substitutes (e.g., exemplar-ideal; The Declaration of Independence—this document), and connectors (e.g., and, despite, if).

Deconstruction

During Deconstruction, teachers introduce mentor texts in a specific genre that students are expected to read and write (e.g., imaginative recount, procedural recount, biographical recount); guide students to deconstruct these texts through demonstration, modeling, and discussions about their purpose, text structures (stages), and language features typical of a specific genre; and build up students' knowledge of the content information (i.e., setting context).

Joint Construction

Teachers and students work together to write a text in the same genre. In this phase, the teacher and students co-construct texts that are similar to the mentor texts that they already explored in the deconstruction phase. Students start using the language features of the specific genre about which they are learning. In co-constructing texts, teachers are expected to provide a bridge for students between their everyday language and the academic language of school so attention will be directed to text organizational issues such as purpose, stages, and language features. The

teacher is typically in front of the room scribing while everyone is writing together.

Collaborative/Independent Construction

Collaborative Construction can be added as a bridge between the joint construction and independent construction phases, especially for students in grades K–2 who are novice writers. Students work with other students in pairs or small groups to construct a text together, brainstorming and negotiating ideas, writing, revising, etc. Teachers continue to support collaborative pairs or groups as needed. *Independent Construction* is a phase in which students are ready to work independently to construct their own texts in the specific genre. Teachers are expected to minimize their support, scaffolding, and guidance so students have more opportunities for their independent writing of the specific genre. These phases of the TLC start with the whole text as the unit in focus rather than individual sentences. Thus, these phases enable teachers to support their students in developing their knowledge and control of school genres across disciplines.

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